

MODES OF INTERPRETATION OF LITERARY TEXTS

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Abstract: Literature as a separate art form is the primary basis for many works of painting, theatre, music and film. This article provides information on the origins of literary interpretation, as well as describing its contemporary forms and interpretations.

Keywords: interpretation, theatrical interpretation, visual interpretation, musical interpretation, film interpretation, fanfiction.

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In Latin the word "interpretatio" means to interpret, to clarify, to translate [4].

For anyone, the process of comprehending the meaning of a text, which is one of the most important types of artistic and linguistic communication, is a kind of dialogue between the speaker, the listener, the writer, and the reader.

The process of understanding the meaning of a text, which is one of the most important types of linguistic communication, is a kind of dialogue between the speaker and the listener, the writer and the reader, in the process of which the meaning embedded in the text, is "distributed" [9]. Today, interpretation is a part of our life and is widely used in such fields as mathematics, psychoanalysis, law, art [5].

Literary interpretation dates back to ancient times. The theatrical productions of ancient Greece are said to have been the first experiences in interpreting literary works.

Literary interpretation has always been influenced by historical reality. In times of political instability, economic decline or, on the contrary, prosperity and economic prosperity of the country, actors of ancient Greece sought to bring something new and as if "from themselves" to the theatrical play, which then consisted of two genres - tragedy and comedy. Depending on the political and economic situation, the play they gave or in a more tragic form, or become even funnier. This was what the audience, whose tastes were influenced by the internal and external situation in the country, demanded of the actors.

The best works of the ancient stage include the works of the famous ancient Greek comedy writer and "father of comedy" Aristophanes, nicknamed the comic

by his contemporaries. The best known works that have come down to us are *The Acharnians*, *The Horsemen*, *The Women at the Feast of Thesmophoria* [1]. [1]. By the way, it is not only the great comedian's plays that have been interpreted; the author himself repeatedly inserted pieces from other texts into his works, making fun of the everyday life of the characters described therein.

From the theatrical productions of ancient Greece, the interpretation of literary works spread to other areas of the arts. People inspired by the literary creations of writers, began to create their own masterpieces based on them. This is how other books, operas, plays, paintings and films gradually emerged. In addition to theatrical interpretation, which is still relevant nowadays, contemporary interpretations of literary works include visual interpretation, musical interpretation, film interpretation and fanfiction [2].

The definition of "visual interpretation of literary works" is not found in any of the contemporary literature, so we can offer the following interpretation of this term: visual interpretation of works of art is the interpretation of literary texts with the help of visual media: drawings, reproductions, photographs, etc. [2]. Today, practically every known literary work has a number of visual interpretations.

The genres in which artists talk about the book can be varied: paintings, drawings, photographs, graphic (computer) works, etc. The artistic interpreters can be famous artists, illustrators, photographers, or unknown authors whose work is filled with the Internet.

Visual interpretations also originated in ancient times. The drawings for Homer's epic poem *The Iliad* can be called the first interpretations of a literary work [2].

In the case of musical works, many are not just closely related to literature, but draw their content from the pages of literature. The notion of "musical interpretation of a literary work" can be defined as a piece of music in any genre or style, based on the plot, characters, or main idea of a literary work. The purpose of musical interpretation is to reveal the writer's intentions through the perspective and imagination of the interpreter.

However, there are so many different possibilities in any literary work that each composer can "tell the story" in his or her own way. He can accentuate the gracefulness or dreaminess of the character, play it sometimes starkly, sometimes loosely, and make the main melody stand out or surround it with melancholy motifs and accompaniment. He can set the semantic accents in his own way, highlight something dynamically, speed up or slow down the tempo a little, and the music will sound different [8].

Thus, the theme of any literary work, conveyed by different composers or songwriters through a musical interpretation, can be "revealed" to the public in a

very different way, because each creative person perceives the author's text in his or her own way.

The jargon "fanfiction" refers to another modern form of literary interpretation. Fanfiction refers to amateur writing based on popular original literary works, as well as works of fiction, comics and computer games. The authors of such works are usually fans of original works who write their stories on a non-commercial basis. It can be a sequel to an original story, a prehistory, a parody, an "alternate universe", a crossover (an interweaving of several works), etc. [11].

In general, fanfiction is written in the fantasy genre and, as previously mentioned, is not intended to be commercial, but there are cases where writers deliberately use the plots of famous books. The purpose of such imitation is to broaden the readership and, of course, to obtain monetary rewards. As an example of a fanfic that touched on classical literature, Roman Parisov's not unknown and much talked about work *Stulik*, written in 2006 and based on the motif.

The book was published in the bestselling novel *Lolita* by Vladimir Nabokov. The vast majority of reviewers referred to this work as nothing less than a "modern *Lolita*" and, naturally, it attracted widespread public interest [3]. Recently, fanfic has moved beyond the realm of literature into the categories of fanpart (a drawn work) and fanfilm (an amateur film based on primary source material) 10.

The next type of literary interpretation, film interpretation, was born in 1902, the year in which the founder of world cinema, Georges Méliès, brought the novel "*Robinson Crusoe*" by Daniel Defoe to the screen [2].

The concept of film interpretation can be interpreted as a creative search for finding and interpreting the meaning and content of a literary text by means of film. In our time, the book has long been considered a companion to the screen, and film interpretation has become an art form in its own right: film art [6].

Today's film interpretations are based on prose, drama, poetry, songs, opera and ballet librettos. Their main goal is to convey the original source material using "The film language is very different from the literary language, so that every literary work is interpreted differently in the films. Some film interpretations, nowadays, are more and more likely to the film adaptations replicate the book, giving the viewer a chance to experience the source material once again, only in a cinematic format. "The film is perhaps the best example of a literal adaptation of the Soviet film industry [7].

In addition to literal adaptation, there is also adaptation based on the work. It is most often used when the book cannot be transferred literally to the screen, for example due to a lack of scope, or when the action in the book is centred on the internal experience of the character, which is difficult to show on screen without conversion into dialogues and events. This type of adaptation is not very faithful to

the source material, but it conveys the main point and adds something new. These types of adaptations are by far the vast majority [7]. Any film interpretation aesthetically enriches the viewer, The book is a good example of a work of literature, whether familiar or unfamiliar. It also contributes to an understanding of the writer's work and its significance in the development of the literary process.

Today, film interpretations of fiction occupy a worthy place in the treasury of world cinema and, viewed from a contemporary perspective, are not inferior to original works in any respect [6].

The first step in this process is to make the work of the theatre, painting, music and cinema the foundation of many works of literature.

The heroes of literary works are so alive that they exist as "familiar acquaintances" in the consciousness of mankind, and the greater the artistic power inherent in their characters, the wider is the range of their interpretations by different types of interpretation. When the reader, viewer or listener "touches" an interpreted literary work, they need the same aesthetic feelings they have already "seen" in the source material. Nowadays, theatre, cinema, opera and other art forms are able to breathe "soul" into works of art, so that the viewer can see living, infinitely moving images of characters and respond to the author's voice "between the lines" in the work the "motives" behind it.

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